

EFFECTIVENESS OF LIRAGLUTIDE (VICTOZA) IN THE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES

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Objective of the study. To evaluate the effectiveness and safety of GLP-1 analogs (Victoza) in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM).

Materials and methods of the study. We examined 15 patients with T2DM at "Mega Ideal Clinic." The average age of the patients was 50.0 ± 4.32 years, with a diabetes duration of 3.6 ± 1.3 years. The body mass index (BMI) was 33.1 ± 1.37 kg/m². All patients were prescribed liraglutide according to the following regimen: 0.6 mg subcutaneously once daily for 7 days, followed by 1.2 mg once daily in combination with metformin. The duration of treatment was 3 months.

Results and discussion. A reduction in subjective and objective symptoms was noted. Complaints such as thirst, frequent urination, and dry mouth decreased. An analysis of the dynamics of carbohydrate metabolism parameters, BMI, and glycated hemoglobin levels after three months of treatment with liraglutide was conducted. The carbohydrate metabolism indicators, including fasting blood glucose, postprandial glycemia, and glycated hemoglobin, changed as follows after treatment: a reduction in glycated hemoglobin from $8.1 \pm 1.2\%$ to $6.2 \pm 1.1\%$; fasting blood glucose decreased from 8.5 ± 1.3 mmol/L to 6.1 ± 1.4 mmol/L; postprandial glucose decreased from 13.1 ± 2.3 mmol/L to 8.3 ± 2.4 mmol/L; BMI decreased from 33.1 ± 6.3 kg/m² to 31.1 ± 4.4 kg/m²; systolic blood pressure decreased from 155 ± 20 mmHg to 145 ± 20 mmHg. No cases of hypoglycemia were observed in any patient. The data obtained demonstrated the effectiveness of liraglutide in the treatment of T2DM.

Conclusions. 1. The use of liraglutide in combination with biguanides leads to a significant positive dynamic in subjective symptoms.
2. Liraglutide significantly reduced fasting glycemia by 27%, postprandial glycemia by 30%, and glycated hemoglobin by 26% ($P \leq 0.05$), while also decreasing the frequency of hypoglycemic conditions.
3. The use of liraglutide resulted in a reduction in BMI.
4. The combination of liraglutide with biguanides does not lead to hypoglycemic conditions.